

Phylogeny of yellowish puffballs and earthballs

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Text

This poster shows additional evidence for transferring *Bovista reunionis* (Kreisel & Hausknecht 2006; type sequenced by Rodrigues et al.) to *Globaria* (following concept of Li et al. 2024) (Fig. 1), the distinct phylogenetic position of *Tortoperdon suspectum* (Yang et al. 2025b) based on ITS-nrLSU-*rpb2* data from its holotype (Figs. 1–2), and phylogenomic support for the sect. *Sclerangium* recently recognized in *Scleroderma* (Yang et al. 2025a) (Fig. 3). They support some interesting points:

1) *Tortoperdon suspectum* is phylogenetically distinct from *Bovista pusilla*, *Holocotylon dermoxanthum*, *Globaria jingningensis*, etc., although it has often been misidentified as these taxa.

2) In the genus *Scleroderma*, sect. *Sclerangium* is a monophyletic group. The sect. *Scleroderma* and sect. *Reticulatae*, already well recognized as monophyletic, are sisters, and sect. *Sclerangium* is sister to the combination of the former two. These patterns may not be strongly supported in single- or few-locus phylograms, but are well supported in the current 1172-locus phylogram. Therefore, when assuming sect. *Sclerangium* to be non-toxic, the toxin in this genus has a single origin by the common ancestor of sect. *Scleroderma* and sect. *Reticulatae*.

Finally, the *rpb2* sequence newly generated from the holotype of *Tortoperdon suspectum* is attached below:

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ggctctgtcaagaacctggcactcatgtcatgtatttccgttggttcatattcggctccggtcatcgaattttggaggagtgggg
ttggagtgcctagaggagaatgcacattcgacgacgccttgtagaaggcttctgtgaacgggtgttggatgggtgttcaccg
tgatctgccaatctcgtaaacaacgatcaagaagctgaggagaaaagatgatattagctcgaagtctccgtggctcgtgaca
ttcgagagaaagagcttaggatttacacggatgcgggtcgtgtctgccggccttattcattgtcgaaaaccagcagctattgt
tacaaaagaagcacattcgctggctgaacaatgggttcgatgaggaagggaacgagtaacaaatgggagcaactgatcaaa
ggcgggtgattgagttgtagacgctgaagaggaggagactgtcatgatttcaatgacaccagaggattggagaactctcg
gttacaagctgctggtgtgatcctcatgcaaacgatggcgagttcgacctcggctcgtctaaaagctggcacacacgctc
acattggacacactgcgagattcatcaagcatgatacttggtatctgtgctagtagtattcattccctgaccacaatcaagt
aag
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▲ **Figure 1.** Phylogeny of Lycoperdaceae inferred from concatenated ITS-nrLSU-rpb2-tef-1α alignment. Nodes are annotated if supported by ≥50% maximum likelihood bootstrap. Collections sequenced in this study / other two concerned collections are highlighted in yellow / tan background, respectively.

▲ **Figure 3.** *Tortoperdon suspectum* and its look-alikes in China. Photos by Kun L. Yang. Bars represent 1 cm.

▲ **Figure 3.** Phylogeny of *Scleroderma* constructed with 1172 full-length single-copy orthologous loci completely present in all sampled genomes by coalescent algorithm. Three major sections are highlighted in different background colors. HTBM collections are sequenced in this study.

References

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